

Direct Visualization Prompts

In this case, the program's source code is explicitly provided to the tool, and the model is instructed to generate a step-by-step visualization of program execution using RAM diagrams. The prompt requires the tool to illustrate how variables are created in memory, how their values change during execution, and how control structures influence program flow. The general template is as follows:

You are an expert in program visualization and Memory Transfer Language (MTL). Given the following program, generate an MTL-based RAM diagrams illustrating the program's execution. The goal is to allow novice programmers to understand how program logic unfolds.

Program source code:

<INSERT A JAVA PROGRAM TO VISUALIZE>

Requirements:

1. Using RAM diagrams, simulate the program execution step by step.
2. After each executable statement, display:
 - the executed statement,
 - the current RAM state.
3. The RAM state shall include:
 - every declared variable or array,
 - each variable's current value,
 - array's element values,
 - parameters and local variables when methods are invoked.
4. Show:
 - variable creation,
 - variable updates,
 - arithmetic results,
 - loop iterations,
 - conditional branch selection,
 - array element modifications,
 - function calls,
 - parameter passing,
 - return values,
 - destruction of local variables after method completion.
5. Preserve the exact execution order of the program.
6. Use a consistent RAM diagram structure throughout the visualization.
7. Do not omit intermediate memory states.
8. Provide concise, step-by-step explanations for each line of code as it executes.
9. The visualization must follow Memory Transfer Language (MTL) principles and represent RAM as accurately as possible.
10. Finish by displaying the final program output and RAM state.

Conceptual Visualization Prompts

In this case, the model is given a programming task described in natural language and is asked to generate both the corresponding program and the associated RAM diagrams illustrating its execution.

You are an expert in program visualization and Memory Transfer Language (MTL). Given the following programming task, suggest a program and generate an MTL-based RAM diagrams illustrating the program's execution. The goal is to allow novice programmers to understand how program logic unfolds.

Programming task:

<INSERT A PROGRAMMING TASK>

Requirements:

1. Generate a program to solve a given task.
2. Using RAM diagrams, simulate the program execution step by step.
3. After each executable statement, display:
 - the executed statement,
 - the current RAM state.
4. The RAM state shall include:
 - every declared variable or array,
 - each variable's current value,
 - array's element values,
 - parameters and local variables when methods are invoked.
5. Show:
 - variable creation,
 - variable updates,
 - arithmetic results,
 - loop iterations,
 - conditional branch selection,
 - array element modifications,
 - function calls,
 - parameter passing,
 - return values,
 - destruction of local variables after method completion.
6. Preserve the exact execution order of the program.
7. Use a consistent RAM diagram structure throughout the visualization.
8. Do not omit intermediate memory states.
9. Provide concise, step-by-step explanations for each line of code as it executes.
10. The visualization must follow Memory Transfer Language (MTL) principles and represent RAM as accurately as possible.
11. Finish by displaying the final program output and RAM state.

Follow-up Prompts

To guide the tool to produce the desired output, one or more prompts can be used accordingly.

Revise the generated RAM diagram to fully comply with Memory Transfer Language (MTL) principles.

Specifically:

- Display the complete RAM state after every executable statement.
- Display all declared variables throughout their scope, including unchanged values.
- Remove unused or empty memory cells.
- Display the values in their designated memory cells.
- Use a consistent diagram layout throughout the visualization.

- Preserve the same ordering of variables or array elements in every RAM state.
- Display the executed statement before each RAM state.
- Show all intermediate execution steps without omission.
- Clearly indicate conditional evaluations and the selected branch.
- Display every loop iteration separately.
- Represent arrays using explicit index-value mappings.
- Display function calls, parameter passing, local variables, return values, and scope changes where applicable.
- Ensure that all explanations accurately correspond to the displayed RAM state.